

REACTIONS OF TETRACHLORIDES OF GROUP IVA ELEMENTS WITH ACETIC ACID

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The reaction of acetic acid with tetrachlorides of silicon, titanium, zirconium and thorium has been studied. The reaction of silicon tetrachloride with acetic acid appears to be straight-forward up to the formation of monochloro-triacetate derivative, when further reaction becomes slow. In the case of titanium tetrachloride, the reaction is direct up to the formation of diacetate product, when side reactions begin to take place, yielding finally a mixture of basic di- and tri-acetates of titanium. The reactions of zirconium and thorium tetrachlorides yield the tetra-acetate products. While thorium tetra-acetate has been shown to be stable to heat under reduced pressure, zirconium tetra-acetate decomposes to yield basic diacetate and acetic anhydride.

It was demonstrated by Montouna (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **49**, 2114) that the reaction between silicon tetrachloride and acetic acid could be represented as :

The reaction of titanium tetrachloride with acetic acid has been shown to furnish a complex basic acetate (Funk and Romer, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1938, **239**, 288). Zirconium and thorium tetrachlorides were shown to react with acetic acid providing their tetra-acetates (Rosenheim and Herzmann, *Ber.*, 1907, **40**, 810; Cleve, *Bull. soc. chim.*, 1874, *ii*, **21**, 116).

A perusal of the above work shows that tetrachlorides of silicon, titanium, zirconium and thorium exhibit a gradual variation in their reactivity with acetic acid (cf. Bradley, Halim and Wardlaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3450). In view of the above, it was considered of interest to make a detailed study of the above reactions. It has been shown that the reaction of silicon tetrachloride with acetic acid is straight-forward in the beginning, but side reactions of the following type begin to take place towards the end :

The reaction of titanium tetrachloride with acetic acid has been found to be straight-forward and exothermic up to the formation of dichloride diacetate product. Further reaction appeared to be complicated and yielded a mixture of basic di- and tri-acetates :

Even in the presence of acetic anhydride, the final end-product is only a basic tri-acetate, and it has not been possible to prepare the tetra-acetate of titanium so far in spite of repeated attempts by different reactions (Pande and Mehrotra, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1957, 114).

The reaction of zirconium tetrachloride with acetic acid was found to yield the tetra-acetate, which decomposed on being heated under reduced pressure:

The reaction of thorium tetrachloride with acetic acid (acetic anhydride also used as the tetrachloride was hydrated) was found to yield thorium tetra-acetate, which was found to be highly stable to heat under reduced pressure.

EXPERIMENTAL

Silicon and titanium tetrachlorides (B.D.H.) were purified by distillation, and zirconium tetrachloride (E. Merck, extra pure) was used without any purification. Acetic acid (E. Merck) was fractionated over a long column and the fraction boiling at 117° was collected and used for the reactions. Extreme precautions were taken to exclude moisture.

Reaction of Silicon Tetrachloride with Acetic Acid

To silicon tetrachloride (23 g.) was added acetic acid (nearly 23 g., molar ratio of silicon tetrachloride:acetic acid=1:4.4). Hydrogen chloride gas was evolved and the reaction mixture became cool. Dry nitrogen gas was bubbled into the reaction mixture in order to expel the HCl gas. After nearly 4 hours, a white crystalline mass was formed. To this was poured dry benzene (nearly 20 c.c.) and nitrogen was again bubbled till the evolution of hydrogen chloride vapours had almost ceased. The supernatant liquid was decanted and the white insoluble product was dried under reduced pressure (4 mm) in a bath at 50°. A white solid was thus obtained. [Found: Si, 12.3; Cl, 13.3. A mixture of SiCl(OAc)_3 and $\text{O [Si(OAc)}_2\text{]}_2$ in the molar ratio of 8:1 requires Si, 11.9; Cl, 12.1%].

This reaction was repeated by taking silicon tetrachloride (11.2 g.) and acetic acid (nearly 12 g., in the molar ratio 1:4.8). In this experiment, instead of nitrogen, a stream of dry air was passed to remove the hydrogen chloride gas. The final end-product (a white solid) was obtained which was found to contain a very little amount of chlorine as compared to the above product. [Found: Si, 12.43. A mixture of Si(OAc)_4 and $\text{O [Si(OAc)}_2\text{]}_2$ in the molar ratio of 1:1 requires Si, 12.22%].

Reaction of Titanium Tetrachloride with Acetic Acid

(i). *With Excess of Titanium Tetrachloride.*—Acetic acid (7.5 g.) was added to titanium tetrachloride (nearly 30 g., molar ratio of acid to tetrachloride = 1 : 1.26). A large amount of heat was developed and the reaction mixture started refluxing with the evolution of dense fumes of hydrogen chloride gas mixed with some titanium tetrachloride. As the reaction mixture cooled down, a yellow solid separated out. After being washed with dry benzene, the solid was dried under reduced pressure. A yellow compound (22 g.) was thus obtained. (Found: Ti, 21.98; Cl, 51.2. $\text{Ti}(\text{OAc})\text{Cl}$, requires Ti, 22.45; Cl, 49.86%). This product is highly deliquescent and is easily soluble in water. On exposure to air it evolves HCl gas.

(ii). *With Excess of Acetic Acid:* (a). *Without refluxing.*—Titanium tetrachloride (3.5 g.) was added to acetic acid (25 c.c.). The reaction mixture became hot and yellow. After some time a pale yellow crystalline mass settled at the bottom of the flask. The supernatant liquid (yellow) containing titanium and chlorine was decanted off and was used in the next experiment (ii, b). After washing the insoluble mass with dry benzene, the product was dried under reduced pressure (3 mm) in a bath at 50°. A pale yellow crystalline mass (1.3 g.) was obtained. [Found: Ti, 19.7; Cl, 27.5. $\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OAc})_2$, requires Ti, 20.22; Cl, 29.93%].

This product is highly deliquescent and is soluble in water, acetone and alcohol and insoluble in benzene. When brought in contact with moisture, it evolved HCl gas.

(b). *With refluxing.*—To the above decanted liquid was added titanium tetrachloride (nearly 2 g.). The reaction mixture containing the crystalline insoluble mass was refluxed in a bath at 130°. Hydrogen chloride gas was evolved and the insoluble mass gradually dissolved giving a clear solution (yellow). After nearly an hour a white precipitate started forming and became thick within a short time during the course of refluxing. It was refluxed for another hour when the evolution of HCl gas almost ceased. The insoluble mass was filtered, washed with benzene (20 c.c.) and dried as usual. The product as a white powder was thus obtained. [Found: Ti, 23.2; Cl, 1.80; OAc, 72.2. An equimolecular mixture of $\text{TiO}(\text{OAc})_2$ and $\text{O}[\text{Ti}(\text{AcO})_2]_2$ requires Ti, 22.1; OAc, 72.7%].

Nearly 2 g. of the product was further refluxed with acetic anhydride (15 c.c.) and acetic acid (3 c.c.) in a bath at 140° for nearly 3 hours. The compound did not show any tendency of dissolving in this mixture. After being washed with dry benzene, the product was dried as usual. [Found: Ti, 20.7; OAc, 75.7. $\text{O}[\text{Ti}(\text{OAc})_2]_2$ requires Ti, 20.55; OAc, 76.0%].

(iii). *Reaction between Titanium Dichloro-diacetate and Acetic Acid (1 M): An Attempt to Prepare Titanium Monochloride Triacetate.*—Acetic acid (1.4 g.) was distilled into the suspension of freshly prepared titanium dichloro-diacetate (5.2 g.) in benzene (30 c.c.), and the mixture refluxed in a bath at 100°. Hydrogen chloride gas was evolved. The evolution continued but became very slow after refluxing

for 8 hours, when the insoluble mass was filtered and dried under reduced pressure (5 mm) at 80°. A white powder (4.6 g.) was obtained. [Found: Ti, 22.1; OAc, 66.3; Cl, 4.0. A mixture of $\text{TiO}(\text{OAc})_2$, $\text{O}[\text{TiCl}(\text{OAc})_2]_2$ and $\text{O}[\text{Ti}(\text{OAc})_2]_2$ in the molar ratio of 3 : 1 : 2 requires Ti, 22.7; OAc, 68.5; Cl, 3.7%].

Reaction of Zirconium Tetrachloride with Acetic Acid

To acetic acid (30 c.c.) was added zirconium tetrachloride (2.6 g.), which dissolved in acetic acid with the evolution of HCl gas and heat. On allowing this reaction mixture to cool down to room temperature, no separation of any insoluble mass was noticed, which was, however, contrary to the reactions of titanium and thorium tetrachlorides with acetic acid. The reaction mixture was therefore refluxed in a bath at 130° for nearly 4 hours. On cooling, a white crystalline product separated out. The supernatant liquid was decanted, the crystalline mass was washed with dry benzene (20 c.c.) and dried under reduced pressure (4 mm) in a bath at 40°. A shining white crystalline product was thus obtained. [Found: Zr, 28.01. $\text{Zr}(\text{OAc})_4$ requires Zr, 27.87%]. This product is soluble in water and in benzene.

Nearly 5 g. of this product was heated in a bath at 150° under reduced pressure (3 mm) for nearly 2 hours. A loss in weight (about 2 g.) was noticed. [Found: Zr, 40.36. $\text{ZrO}(\text{OAc})_2$ requires Zr, 40.4%].

Reaction of Thorium Chloride with Acetic Acid

To the hydrated thorium tetrachloride (7 g.) was added a mixture of acetic acid (25 c.c.) and acetic anhydride (nearly 10 c.c.). The reaction mixture became clear and hot. Immediately an insoluble mass started forming. The reaction mixture was refluxed for nearly 2 hours in a bath at 130°. The supernatant liquid was decanted and the insoluble mass was dried under reduced pressure (3 mm) in a bath at 70°. A white crystalline product (nearly 7 g.) was obtained. [Found: Th, 49.34; OAc, 50.01. $\text{Th}(\text{OAc})_4$ requires Th, 49.6; OAc, 50.4%].

The above product (4 g.) was heated for nearly 2 hours under reduced pressure in a bath at 130-40° and no loss in the weight was observed. (Found: Th, 49.36; OAc, 50.02%). This treatment clearly indicates that contrary to zirconium tetra-acetate, thorium tetra-acetate is stable to heat.

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